

HISTORICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE PLACE AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ART OF OPERA IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *The place of opera art in Uzbekistan and the historical description of its development stages were covered by biographical information.*

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The first Uzbek operas began to appear in the second half of the 1930s. These were the opera "The Storm" by S. Vasilenko and M. Ashrafiy and the operas "Layli and Majnun" by R. Gliyer and T. Sadikov. The opera "The Tempest" is a large work in five acts, and its content reflects the conflicts of the Uzbek people with the tsarist government that took place in Jizzakh in 1916. Even though the uprising was suppressed, the main goal of the work remains the aspirations of the Uzbek people for freedom.

Russian intellectuals have been living in Turkestan for many years and as a result of their interest in art, a Russian opera theater will be opened in Tashkent. One of the main reasons for the establishment of the opera theater was the tour (creative tour) of the Italian opera group in Tashkent in 1900. The Italians introduced operas

such as "Rigoletto", "Traviata", "Troubadour", "Carmen", "Payatsi", "Faust" to Russian intellectuals in Tashkent.

At the same time, Russian intellectuals laid the foundation for the establishment of the Russian opera theater by performing symphonic works of Western and Russian classical composers, excerpts from operas, symphonic suites in their concert programs. The first performances of the Opera Theater were "Rusalka" by Dargomijsky and "Eugene Onegin" by Tchaikovsky.

Due to the wide spread of the opera genre, Verdi's Rigoletto, Gouno's Faust, Rubenstein's Demon, Tchaikovsky's Pikovaya dama, Mussorgsky's Boris Godunov, Borodin's Prince Igor, Verdi's La Traviata, and Verdi's "Faust" were performed on the stage of the Russian Opera Theater. Aida, Puccini's "Bohemia", Rossini's "Sevilsky Serulnik" saw the stage. The artists of the Russian Opera Theater organized performances in the regions of Uzbekistan and began to promote the art of opera among the Uzbek people, and these services became the basis for the establishment of Uzbek operas.

During the 40s and 50s, several opera works were staged on the stage of the State Opera and Ballet Theater named after Alisher Navoi. His repertoire includes Russian and foreign operas and ballets, as well as works by composers of brotherly nations. D. Kabalevsky's "Taras Family", T. Khrennikov's "Boronda", G. Mayboroda's "Arsenal" and A. Kozlovsky's "Ulugbek" operas created in Uzbekistan are among them.

But the most important of the problems that were highlighted was the creation of national Uzbek operas and their staging. That is why several Uzbek national operas were created and performed on the theater stage during 1947-1967. Operas staged in previous years: "Great Canal" by S. Vasilenko and M. Ashrafiy, "Gulsara" by R. Gliyer and T. Sadikov, "Takhir and Zukhro" by T. Jalilov and B. Brovsin, " by G. Mushel and V. Uspenskiy" In addition to Farkhod and Shirin operas, newly created Uzbek national operas are gradually created in the opera genre of musical art and appear on the stage.

These are "Dilorom" by M. Ashrafi, "Song of Khorazm" by M. Yusupov, "Zaynab and Amon" by D. Zakirov, "Song of Khorazm" by T. Sodikov, B. Zeidman, Yu. Rajabi, D. Zakirov. "Heart of a Poet" by Ashrafi, "Zulmatdan Zia" by R. Hamroyev are works.

Among the works mentioned above, the opera "Dilorom" from the poem "Sa'bai Sayyor" by A.Navoi, dramatists K.Yashin and Mumtaz Muhammedov, and the services of composer M. Ashrafi in creating a modern work from Uzbek classical literature took a special place in Uzbek music culture. The opera "Dilorom" consisting of four acts and seven scenes will be performed on the stage of the State Opera and Ballet Theater named after A. Navoi. The events take place against the background of the ruthlessness of the king and the officials towards the people, the rebellion of the people against the oppression, and the struggle against the king Bahram and his associates who wanted to take Dilorom by force. Dilorom disobeys the cruel king and saves his honor and love by sacrificing his life.

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